
TEACHING LISTENING WITH TECHNOLOGY

Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan

named after Mirzo Ulug'bek

*The faculty of psychology, the department of Foreign languages: Philology and
teaching languages: English*

Scientific advisor:

Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla qizi

Student of group 101-23:

Amirova Xurshida Abduaziz qizi

Abstract: Language teachers have long used technology to practice listening. From more traditional media such as analog audio and language labs to newer, Internet-based media, technology helps provide learners with authentic and realistic experiences that add excitement to the learning process and increase their contact with the language. In this article, I will show Internet-based media Audio technology exposes students to a variety of speakers, voices, accents, situations, and rich cultural content, and it affords additional practice outside the classroom. It is easy to access and use at low or no cost. Not only does it save a teacher's energy and voice, it offers a listener a certain degree of control over listening.

Keywords: Internet-based media, Audio technology, iTunes University, Academic Earth, and MIT Open Courseware, Voice of America, BBC, CNN, and Spotlight Radio listening websites for ESOL, OhMyNews, ESL Podcast, and Breaking News English, Acknowledgements.

Audio technology can add interest to language instruction in several ways. For example, a longer passage can be divided into manageable portions by pausing at

natural breaks. A teacher can also pause listening to ask students to predict what they might hear next, write an answer, transcribe a sentence, or simply repeat after the speaker for pronunciation practice. Recording parts of an audio segment separately can lead to an information-gap activity in which groups of students each listen to a part of the text and try to reconstruct the whole story together. An abundance of listening materials available in many different formats makes it easy to find an appropriate text for any student population. Some technology-based activities primarily focus on listening and others naturally combine listening and speaking, but most of them extend to practice of other language skills and strategies. They are easy to sequence and integrate into any curriculum, can be adjusted depending on the level of language proficiency, and work well in or out of class. Following are the most popular and widely accepted teachers' choices that can be used to teach listening comprehension in a variety of classroom settings:

- > songs
- > audio books
- > radio (e.g., Voice of America, BBC, CNN, and Spotlight Radio)
- > listening websites for ESOL (e.g., The English Listening Lounge, Randall's ESL Cyber Listening Lab, English Language video (e.g., commercials, documentaries, feature films, shows, and educational videos for native and nonnative speakers of English))
- > podcasts (e.g., OhMyNews, ESL Podcast, and Breaking News English)
- > academic lectures (e.g., iTunes University, Academic Earth, and MIT Open Courseware)

Active Empathetic Listening: Is it Possible Online?

With the challenges presented by technology, how can we become better active empathetic listeners? First, when interacting, regardless of medium, practice respect, especially if someone is speaking. Respect can be displayed by simply treating the person as a unique individual with a distinct background, experiences, feelings, and thoughts. In an interaction, respect can be manifested when a person's worth is maintained, regardless of the content of the conversation.

Second, practicing genuineness in the conversation can help reduce "fake" communication. When interacting, one might be tempted to be phony or not being one's true self to maintain one's professional identity, but this can interfere with the listening process. To maintain genuineness, one needs to match one's listening behaviors with another's feelings.

Third, build rapport and establish trust. Avoid deceptive communication or telling lies, this will only establish distrust. One can build rapport by finding things in common with the other person and engaging in self-disclosure by sharing personal stories. Trust can be established by being reliable and trustworthy, for instance, if you indicate that you will complete a report at work by a deadline, you will need to do this to establish trust.

Technology-based media make teaching and learning more accessible and easy, to begin with. Future teachers should integrate this technology-based since it creates collaboration and enhances the students' listening skills; it raises awareness about the technology, and students can learn a lot from it and be creative on their own. Furthermore, future researchers should consider this technology-based media, which proves helpful. The purpose of this technology-based is to allow educators, readers, and researchers to consider this and make a way to integrate this into the education system. Many arguments talk about the integration of technology since it removes or lessens the old traditional way of teaching, yet most of them believe that

it connects them to one with a common goal. Technology has an essential role in the process of teaching. We know that any advancement in technology directly or indirectly has been influential in teaching and learning methods. Listening is the process of interpreting and understanding what we hear. It is a conscious effort and requires focus to understand and digest the information thoroughly. Good listening skills allow us to perform better, for it is the key to effective communication. Good listening is the makers of ideas, and it involves the processing of incoming data. Jalongo (2012) states that it is essential to enhance and develop the learning process. This ability, along with other macro skills, enables attention to sound and construct meaning. whereas traditional equipment (e.g., audio and video players) may be primarily operated by a teacher, Internet-based technologies often require an active participation on the part of learners. It is important that teachers assess students' knowledge about computers before engaging them in an activity and provide training for those who are less familiar with technology. Students with no previous exposure to computers will need several training sessions to develop keyboard and mouse skills and learn some basic terminology. Provide a worksheet detailing the steps needed to accomplish an Internet-based activity to the entire class, even to experienced Internet users. Incorporating technology in teaching listening skills significantly impacts achieving a successful learning process. Various technological tools benefit from

Podcast Application in Teaching Listening

There are numerous ways to use technology-based media in teaching listening skills because it makes the teaching easier and allows students to engage in an activity where they feel excited about the lesson that will be tackled. However, teaching listening skills is not that easy since it requires patience and good speaking and listening skills. In teaching listening skills, a teacher should be clear with the objective and focus on his/her purpose, and one of the technology-based media that can be used to teach listening skills is the use of podcast application since podcast

Based on the study, the existing learning media requires development to be more accessible, used, and understood. Lots of audio media were made to provide flexible learning tools. The more books discussed, the easier it is a media called a podcast. Podcasts have become an application widely used today to get desired information. Teachers should have a new strategy in listening teaching to help their students be more active and master the learning process. So, the researcher tries to use podcasts to develop students' listening skills. Also, listening is essential to develop a robust and expressive response. Other listening is the process of receiving spoken or non-two verbal messages, building meaning from them, and responding to them.

Radio News in the Teaching Listening

Technology brings much impact on our lives, specifically on education. As we live in this fast-changing world, various technology-based exist, and some are still waiting to discover. Incorporating technological tools in the classroom engage learners to be more motivated and interested in their learning. Teachers can produce, create and enhance their lessons using different digital tools. Lots of media are present to help develop and enhance macro skills. Listening skills are essential parts of macro skills that need to improve. According to Willis (2018), good communication skills go beyond listening. By focusing on what others are saying or what we hear around us, we can conclude the information or messages. Listening also requires effort to avoid misunderstandings.

Mobile Based Media As the Solution in Teaching and Learning Listening

Skills

This research article entitled Mobile-Based Media as the Solution in Teaching and Learning Listening Skills by Elfiona et al. (2019), discusses the appropriate technology-based media used to help teachers and students to resolve their difficulties in understanding and to learn listening skills in the teaching and learning process in the learning environment. Wherein it presented in this study that according to several senior high schools in Padang, both teachers and students

have limited media and less opportunity to practice listening, which became problems and barriers for them to learn. Therefore, this research article explains the importance of mobile-based media in teaching listening skills which are the mobile phone and the mobile applications contained therein.

CONCLUSION:

In today's new era, technology plays a significant role, especially in the field of education in the teaching and learning process in the learning environment, that gives real and meaningful help in achieving the intended learning goals by using the appropriate technology-based media in the teaching and learning process. This paper, entitled *Technology-Based Media Used in Teaching Listening Skills: A Recent Literature Review*, discussed the appropriate technology-based media that can make teachers' teaching effective and productive in teaching listening skills and lead the students to have productive growth and development in enhancing their listening skills. Every research study contained in this paper has emphasized the effective use of mobile devices and mobile applications as media used in teaching listening skills, which in turn has resulted in the efficient implementation of technology-based media in teaching listening skills that enabled both teachers and students to successfully and effectively have authentic learning experiences. The technology-based media used in this paper are Mobile-Based Media, Multimedia Technology, Podcast Applications, Radio News, and Mobile-Based Audiobooks, which discuss and demonstrate the teaching and learning of listening skills to provide solutions to learning problems experienced by both teachers and students in learning listening skills. In this paper, the listening difficulties experienced by both teachers and students in the teaching and learning process in studying listening skills are explained to provide the solution. Also, the requirement to use appropriate promising results that those research articles used and contained in this paper give positive results and good impact to both teachers and students in improving their listening skills and resolving listening difficulties. This paper shows students and

teachers as they become productive individuals who have gained knowledge in understanding and learning listening skills as they are exposed to accomplish tasks and learn discussions with the implementation of appropriate technology-based media in teaching listening skills. Using appropriate technology-based media in the teaching and learning process in teaching listening skills is an important thing that brings interactive learning experiences to students.

REFERENCES:

- ✓ Andriyani, A. S., Maulina, M., Amin, S., Nasrullah, R., Asdar, A., & Hamsiah, A.
- ✓ (2022). Students' perception in learning English through blended learning. *Journal of Education and Teaching (JET)*, 3(1), 50-68.
- ✓ <https://doi.org/10.51454/jet.v3i1.138>
- ✓ Ampa, A. T. (2015). The Implementation of Interactive Multimedia Learning
- ✓ Materials in Teaching Listening Skills. *English Language Teaching*, 8(12),
- ✓ 56. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v8n12p56>
- ✓ Azar, A. S., & Nasiri, H. (2014). Learners' Attitudes toward the Effectiveness of
- ✓ Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) in L2 Listening
- ✓ Comprehension. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 98, 1836–
- ✓ 1843.
- ✓ Demir, M. D., & Tivil, Z. M. (2021). The effect of technology-based materials on
- ✓ vocational high school students' listening skill. *Dil ve Dilbilimi Çalışmaları*
- ✓ *Dergisi*, 17(1), 448–457. <https://doi.org/10.17263/jlls.903469>
- ✓ Elfiona, E., Zaim, M., & Refnaldi, R. (2019). Mobile-Based Media as the Solution

- ✓ in Teaching and Learning Listening Skill. Journal of Physics: Conference Series, 1(1387), 1-6.
- ✓ Jalongo, M. R. (1995). Promoting Active Listening in the Classroom. Childhood Education, 72(1), 13–18.
- ✓ Lar, M. A. M., & Maulina, M. (2021). Students' self-confidence in speaking for a live presentation: A literature review. Klasikal: Journal of Education, Language Teaching and Science, 3(3), 88-95.

- ✓ has something to do with the sound. The study entitled “The effectiveness of podcast application in teaching listening” proves that it is helpful to integrate this technology-based since it helps students enhance their listening skills. The researchers conducted a study and survey questionnaire to know the students' response to the use of podcasts, and the result says that most of the students conclude that it is adequate to use.

- ✓ becoming a better listener. These tools prioritize improving learners' ability to comprehend and interpret what they hear deeply. Learners can use this multimedia to interact with others, learn at their best and understand their environment. Additionally, teachers can create more mindful and interactive discussions lessons. Using digital tools, they can quickly provide information and knowledge to their students most interestingly and enjoyably

Moreover, it is not hard for everyone to adjust to using technology as we live in the modern era, and it is now part of our daily lives. However, active listening is possible if distractions can be minimized. These barriers include physical noise, auditory and visual distractions. Hence, this can be minimized by integrating appropriate techniques and strategies. For example, pay attention to what is heard and relocate to a quiet place